

THE VERB PHRASE WITH A DEPENDENT COMPONENT EXPRESSED BY THE PRONOUN

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Abstract: Thesis deals with the structure of a word phrase in English verbal phrase components in personal and possessive pronouns and will be analyzed through scientific research.

Key words: Phrase, verbal phrases, noun phrase, dependent component, transitive verb, intransitive verb, personal pronoun, reflexive pronouns, demonstrative pronouns.

Introduction

Noun and verb phrases are the two most crucial parts of a sentence. Noun phrases identify the objects or people present in a circumstance. Verbs describe what the objects or individuals named by the noun phrases are doing to one another, how they are related to one another, and other details. [1.p-7]

All clauses in English have at least two parts, a noun phrase (subject) and a verb phrase:

Noun phrase (subject)	Verb phrase
<i>The Parents</i>	<i>Laughed</i>
<i>The flowers</i>	<i>were painted</i>

According to B. Ilyish, a phrase is any grouping of two or more words that functions as a grammatical unit but is not an analytical form of a word (such as, for example, the perfect forms of verbs). Ilyish continues, "A basic distinction must be made between a phrase and a sentence. Just like a word, a phrase can be used to name a phenomena or process. According to the grammatical categories represented in a sentence, each component may experience grammatical alterations. Without diluting the phrase's meaning."

"Things are very different when using a sentence. However, it becomes challenging to accept Ilyish's notion of phrases when one realizes that every phrase is a component of sentences. [2.p-9]

However, it becomes challenging to accept Ilyish's notion of phrases when one realizes that every phrase is a component of sentences. A phrase's structure can

change without necessarily changing the sentence it refers to. In this instance, that sentence will be changed into another sentence in accordance with the author's idea.

It is possible to use the categorization of the head verb (the phrase's head component) as a basic guideline for categorizing verbal phrases into transitive and intransitive forms.

It is possible to refer to a dependent component as an object component when it appears in a transitive verb. There are many types of verb phrases and several different types of pronouns in English language. These are: personal pronouns, reflexive pronouns, possessive pronouns, indefinite pronouns, relative pronouns and demonstrative pronouns.

The head component of a phrase can be distinguished from its dependent Component because it determines many of the grammatical features of a phrase as a whole. For instance, in the sentence "*That man saw my sister in Moscow*", the phrase "*man saw my sister*" is a verbal phrase which is expressed by the Possessive pronoun "*my*". [4.p-110]

The other type of verb phrase is shown by the following example:

'We (she and I) are sleeping'. This sentence consists of just a verb phrase. This type of verb phrase is called an independent pronoun verb phrase. It consists of three parts. The first part, represented by '*we (she and I)*' is the subject pronoun. The second part, represented by "*are 'present progressive'*" is the tense marker. The last part, represented by verb '*to sleep*', is the head of the verb phrase. [5.p-54]

Verbal phrase can express various relations in the sentences. One of them is a verbal phrase with the dependent component expressed by the Personal pronoun by model "*V+ P+ object*" in modern English, in such cases head component of the use with the meaning

For examples:

- 1) To sell- Shop assistant sold them by weight.
- 2) To keep - Because she can keep you safe.
- 3) To love- He loves you eternally.
- 4) To believe- We believe them without doubt.
- 5) To forget- He had forgotten us
- 6) To miss- Mother miss her daughter too much.
- 7) To look- Children look at the window immediately.
- 8) To come- Her friends came to see her last week.

In these examples all the dependent components of the phrase are in the objective case. It can be considered that, every combination of two or more words constitutes a unit which they term "phrase" to combination of notional words and do not draw a distinction between the two types of word groups and one of the types of subordinate phrases is the verbal phrases. Verbal phrases are very important in syntactical structure of modern English. They are characterized with different using structural types, with combining create compound constructions.

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